

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Komila Shoyimova O'rol qizi

TERMS THAT ARE CHARACTERISTIC OF TRANSLATING

BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TRADITIONS

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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